

MEDICAL SCIENCES

CHALLENGES LEADING TO DELAYS IN ESTABLISHING THE DIAGNOSIS OF EXTRANODAL AGGRESSIVE NON-HODGKIN LYMPHOMA

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Abstract

What is not yet known on the issue addressed in the submitted Manuscript

Despite the development of new methods of diagnosis and treatment with antineoplastic agents, the results of aggressive NHL treatment remain modest, with frequent relapses and primary refractory forms.

Research hypothesis

It was carried out a qualitative, analytical study, with a narrative synthesis of the literature, as well as studying the group of patients included in the study to detect the challenges that lead to the delay in establishing the diagnosis of aggressive extranodal NHL.

The novelty added by manuscript to the already published scientific literature

Conducting a broad literature synthesis to demonstrate the importance of continuing research in the field of extranodal aggressive NHL, which remains a current problem of contemporary hemato-oncology and public health.

Introduction: Non-Hodgkin's lymphomas form a group of malignant tumors, which develop from extramedullary hematopoietic cells. They are one of the most common forms of hemoblastosis. Diseases can develop in people of any age. The morbidity of NHL increases with age reaching the highest level in people over 50 years of age.

The aim of the study was to identify the causes that lead to difficulties in establishing the diagnosis of aggressive extranodal non-Hodgkin's lymphoma.

Material and methods:

It was carried out a qualitative, analytical study. The article assumed both the research of the specialized literature and the processing of the information within the research group in order to present the most conclusive data related to the current problems in establishing the diagnosis of aggressive extranodal NHL.

Results:

Aggressive extranodal NHL remains a major problem, with a clear increase in the annual number of cases globally. This trend is observed in several countries of the world, thus morbidity increases by 3% annually in women and by 4% in men. Worldwide, aggressive NHL continues to predominantly affect the working population. Although patients with primary extranodal NHL tend to present to the medical specialist at a lower stage than those with primary nodal disease, the number of those presenting at advanced stages continues to remain high.

Conclusions:

Although the diagnosis of NHL does not involve great impediments, patients are often detected in the late stages of the disease either because of late referral to a doctor or because of incorrect diagnosis by primary care physicians. Despite the development of new methods of diagnosis and treatment, extranodal aggressive NHL continues to be a current problem of clinical medicine and public health, requiring increased managerial and financial efforts.

Keywords: aggressive non-Hodgkin's lymphomas, extranodal, morbidity, diagnosis

Introduction

Non-Hodgkin's lymphomas (NHL) represent a heterogeneous group of malignant tumors of B-, T- and

rarely, NK-cell origin that can primarily affect any organ and tissue containing lymphoid cells [1]. Currently, NHL are considered as the most common

group of malignant hemopathies, so they rank 7th in terms of morbidity from malignant tumors and 6th in terms of cancer mortality [2]. Worldwide, there is a clear increase in the incidence of NHL by approximately 80% more than at the beginning of the 70s [3]. Annually, 287,000 new cases of NHL are diagnosed worldwide[4]. The incidence of NHL varies significantly by geographic region, these differences may be related to demographics, environmental differences and other factors such as lifestyle, health behaviors and healthcare systems[5]. A higher incidence is found in the male gender, especially in Israel (17.6 cases per 100 thousand), in white Americans (14.5 per 100 thousand), in Australia (15.3 per 100,000), Canada (13.7 per 100 thousand) and Portugal (13.3 per 100 thousand)[6]. The similar geographical peculiarity was also observed in the female sex, with a higher incidence recorded in the population of Israel (13.0 per 100,000), white Americans (10.4 per 100 thousand), in Canada (10.0 per 100 thousand), Australia (12.3 per 100 thousand) and lower – in Middle Africa (2.8 per 100 thousand), South Africa (1.6 per 100 thousand), Vietnam (3.5 per 100 thousand), India (3.6 per 100 thousand)[7]. The NHL morbidity index in the Republic of Moldova is 4.1 per 100,000 population[8].

The aim of the study was to identify the causes that lead to difficulties in establishing the diagnosis of aggressive extranodal non-Hodgkin's lymphoma.

Material and methods:

It was carried out a qualitative, analytical study. The article assumed both the research of the specialized literature and the processing of the information within the research group in order to present the most conclusive data related to the current problems in establishing the diagnosis of aggressive extranodal NHL.

The article synthesized and systematized various primary studies, dedicated to the epidemiological and diagnostic aspects of aggressive extranodal non-Hodgkin lymphomas. The accumulation of information for this research was carried out by analyzing data from specialized international bibliographic sources and official statistics on the respective malignant myeloproliferative neoplasm. To achieve the formulated aim, scientific medical publications were searched over GoogleSearch, PubMed, Z-Library, NCIB, Medscape, Hinari Database, by keywords: "Non Hodgkin lymphoma", "aggressive", "extranodal", "mortality", "survival", "incidence", "prevalence", "diagnosis". More than 50 bibliographic reference sources were studied, to carry out a qualitative research. At the same time, research was carried out in the group of 99 patients from the Oncological Institute of the Republic of Moldova. The obtained data were compared with those from the specialized literature and with other studies conducted in other countries.

Results and Discussion:

Aggressive extranodal NHL remains a major current problem, with a clear increase in the annual number of cases globally. The evolution and survival rate largely depend on the type and type of lymphoma, the stage of the disease, the presence of signs of intoxication, the age of the patient at the time of the

diagnosis, concomitant pathologies. Although patients with primary extranodal NHL tend to present themselves to the specialist in a lower stage than those with primary lymph node disease, the number of those who are addressed in the advanced stages continues to remain high. At the moment, contemporary diagnostic methods allow the exact stabilization of the diagnosis and subsequently the initiation of treatment according to the type of lymphoma.

NHL develops and disseminates at different rates, being divided according to histopathological and clinical-evolutionary characteristics into indolent and aggressive [9]. Aggressive lymphomas are a heterogeneous group of malignant tumors that reflect clinical, biological and pathological diversity[16]. They refer to those subtypes that grow rapidly (proliferative index KI-67 > 40%) and would often be lethal within months without appropriate therapy [10]. According to data from the American Society of Hematology in 2015, aggressive lymphoma constituted approximately 60% of all NHL cases in the United States [11].

There are different types and subtypes of aggressive NHL. To be able to apply an effective treatment, it is essential to establish the type and subtype of lymphoma. Sometimes, more than 1 type of lymphoma can be detected in the same patient[22]. Initially, it will be established in which cell type the pathology started[19]. B-cell lymphoma is the most common, about 90% of people in Western countries are diagnosed with B-cell lymphoma. T-cell lymphomas account for about 10%, and are more common in Asian countries. While NK cell lymphoma affects less than 1% of people who suffer from this disease[23].

The most common subtype of aggressive NHL that develops from B cells type is diffuse large B-cell lymphoma (DLBCL)[25]. 30% of NHL in the United States is of the DLBCL type, it tends to develop extranodally in about 40% [24]. Also from B cells, mantle cell lymphoma develops, affecting from 5 to 7% of people with lymphoma. It usually develops in people over the age of 60 and is much more common in men than women, usually involving the bone marrow in the process[3].

Primary mediastinal large B-cell lymphoma is an aggressive form of DLBCL, often complicated by superior vena cava syndrome. This subtype of lymphoma is most commonly found in women between the ages of 30 and 40, and about 2.5% of people with NHL have this subtype[2].

Another subtype of lymphoma that develops from T and NK cells is peripheral T-cell lymphoma, not otherwise specified NOS. This is an aggressive form of lymphoma that is often advanced when doctors detect it[26]. It mostly affects people over the age of 60 and accounts for about 6% of all lymphomas in the United States and Europe. Another subtype of aggressive lymphoma is anaplastic lymphoma. This aggressive form of lymphoma accounts for approximately 2% of all lymphomas and approximately 10% of all childhood lymphomas[30].

In our clinic, the most frequent type of aggressive lymphoma turned out to be lymphoblastic in 55.5%,

followed by diffuse large B-cell lymphoma - 33.3%, T-cell lymphoma was diagnosed in 7.07%, and the others types of lymphoma (NOS lymphoma, grade IIIB follicular, from the mantle zone, plasmablastic) each of them constituting less than 1% [figure. 1].

Tumor originating in extranodal tissue is termed primary extranodal lymphoma (ENL), while hematogenous spread of disease from lymph nodes to extranodal tissue is secondary extranodal lymphoma[12]. The incidence of ENL is continuously increasing in recent years, there are numerous factors that "favor" this increase: HIV infection, the increasing use of immunosuppressive therapy and indole viral infection [27]. Following the study realised in the Department of Hematology in the Republic of Moldova, it was found that the gastrointestinal tract (TGI) is more frequently affected - 37.35%, of its anatomical segments, the most frequently involved in the process is the stomach (32.3%). The 2nd place among the extranodal locations is occupied by the Waldeyer lymphatic ring - 24.24%, of the formations of the ring, the involvement of the nasopharynx was most often observed - 13.13%, followed by the damage to the palatine tonsils - 10.1%. Soft tissues as primary damage by NHL were observed in 7.07%, followed by skin and bone tissue each returning 6.06%, CNS - 4.4%, and the other locations (lacrimal gland, mammary gland, liver, kidneys, testicle, parotid gland, etc.) constitute on average less than 1% each [figure. 2].

The only method to confirm the diagnosis of NHL remains the excisional biopsy of the focus with subsequent morphological, immunohistochemical, flow-cytometry, FISH examination for the histological determination of the lymphoma subtype.

However, the most frequent causes of the late establishment of the diagnosis are the late referral of the patient to the doctor, being observed in 58% of cases in our study, as well as the confusion of the diagnosis by other doctors in 23% of cases, often treating the disease as an inflammatory/reactive process, and redirecting the patient to a hematologist after several treatment attempts with anti-inflammatory preparations/antibiotic therapy 16%, which ultimately leads to an increase in the number of patients detected in stages III-IV [figure. 3].

Worldwide, NHL caused 6.8 million DALYs (disability-adjusted life-years) in 2016 [21]. Despite the development of new antineoplastic agents, the results of aggressive NHL treatment remain modest, with frequent relapses and primary refractory forms[17]. Patient survival differs depending on the stage of pathology at the time of diagnosis, the type and subtype of lymphoma, the presence of signs of intoxication, age, concomitant pathologies[28]. According to a study realised in the UK between 2004 and 2016, 60 out of 100 DLBCL patients survive 5 years or more after diagnosis, while 55 out of 100 Burkitt lymphoma patients survive about 5 years and only 35 out of 100 patients with T-cell lymphoma survive up to 5 years after diagnosis[29].

The increase in morbidity and disability in the working population, the considerable rate of late diagnosis of NHL and the modest results of the treatment of aggressive histopathological types [19, 20] remain a current problem of clinical medicine and public health, requiring increased managerial and financial efforts.

Conclusions:

1. NHL occupies the first place in the structure of morbidity through malignant hemopathies, the incidence of which shows a continuous increase in recent years.

2. Worldwide, there is an increase in aggressive NHL morbidity rates in the able-bodied population, as well as an increase in the degree of disability.

3. Although the diagnosis of NHL does not involve great impediments, patients are often detected in the late stages of the disease either because of late referral to a doctor or because of incorrect diagnosis by primary care physicians.

4. Despite the development of new methods of diagnosis and treatment, aggressive extranodal NHL continues to constitute a current problem of clinical medicine and public health, requiring increased managerial and financial efforts.

Declaration of conflicting interests

The author declares that he is not in conflict of financial or non-financial interests for the data and information presented in the manuscript.

Figure 1 - Prevalence of aggressive NHL in the Hematology Department of the Oncology Institute

Figure 2 - Extranodal lesions of aggressive NHL

Figure 3 - Causes of delay in diagnosis

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